

Digitalization in Higher Education: An Analysis of Academics Adoption of Online Teaching

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Abstract – This article illustrates how the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) examined the adoption of online teaching by higher education academics. Data from a range of lecturers were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and SPSS software to understand factors affecting technology adoption. These factors include Ease of Use, Utility, Attitudes Toward Online Teaching, and Behavioral Intention. Results indicate that both Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) significantly shape positive attitudes and intentions towards the integration of online teaching platforms. Although the discussion underscores the importance of enhancing user experience and perceived value to improve adoption rates, overall, the study provides valuable insights for policymakers and educational leaders, recommending investments in technological infrastructure and comprehensive faculty training programs. While the research offers significant contributions to understanding technology acceptance in higher education, it also identifies limitations related to sample diversity and generalizability, suggesting directions for future research.

Keywords: digitalization, technology acceptance, academics, higher education, e-learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid digitalization of higher education poses both challenges and opportunities for institutions worldwide. This article explores the adoption and utilization of online teaching by higher education academics through the lens of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Focusing on the comprehensive study particularly detailed in Chapter 5 (Results and analysis) of the recent thesis, this examination sheds light on the critical factors influencing academics readiness and willingness to integrate digital technology into their teaching practices.

A. *Overview of the structure of the article*

The overall study is explained, covering the Model of the study and methods used for research design and data analysis. The results are summarized, leading to a discussion on interpreting the findings and their impact on online teaching. The article also considers the limitations of the study and offers ideas for further research. Recommendations are given for decision-makers and institutional leaders.

II. BACKGROUND OF DIGITALIZATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

The trend of adopting advanced technology and flexible learning continues to grow in the field of education as digitalization takes center stage. Options for teaching and learning, such as e-learning, online learning, blended learning, and the utilization of learning management systems (LMS), are among the modalities being embraced [17]. The move to online teaching was sped up by the COVID-19 crisis, requiring a quick adjustment to teaching techniques [3]. This shift brings advantages like better access and enhanced educational results, but it also comes with challenges, such as the necessity of having proper technological infrastructure in place and regular training programs [1].

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

In most Western regions of the world universities make significant investments towards e-learning. However, although academics are found to engage with the online environment, they rarely utilize the digital tools that encourage collaborative participation. Virtual interchanges are hardly ever exploited by academics efficiently. In fact, the digital teaching platforms are simply used to deposit usual and/or additional learning material ([16], [20]). On the other hand, technical challenges are not rare and few. Such challenges include the obtainability of fitting hardware and software programs, accessible technological support, lack of digital and technological knowledge and skills, complex software programs, connectivity issues, video-conferencing technology requires proper infrastructure, and teaching aids that are constructive in a traditional context are usually ineffectual in the online environment [9].

Similar challenges are noted in Africa but are largely due to lack of and/or impeded technological developments at institutional level and country-wide at large. Challenges experienced by tertiary institutions include major lack of financial support from country governance and leadership, curtailed internet connectivity levels, unequal supply of electricity hinders the amalgamation of digital technologies, not enough access to computers for lecturers to connect with students, and lack of digital and technological training [18]. In some regions national power supply is tapered to sectors that are more economically viable as a result individuals more especially learners in non-metropolitan areas are bordered out [21]. A vast majority of higher education academics are found to be technologically less learned in addition to lacking and/or having no technological resources in their teaching environments [7]. Research in South Africa shows that largely amongst academics there is negative attitude towards online teaching and various formerly deprived tertiary institutions are not yet technologically exploited [15]. Academics appear to have more faith in conventional didactic practices; however, some are glad to take advantage of the online convenience. For instance, spending time on mandated research work while interacting with students online. However, utilization is still truncated due to lack of digital and technological knowledge and skills, scarce provision of training, and more particularly many academics found that online in certain faculty or subject matter is challenging in view of the particular type didactic needs and practices [11].

IV. STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Regardless of the benefits of teaching through digital means, there seems to be a lack of consistency among higher education academics when it comes to fully utilizing online tools for education. Barriers like inadequate training, lack of support, and reluctance to embrace change play a role in this challenge [4]. Being aware of these challenges is crucial in developing strategies to support higher education academics in integrating digital tools into their instructional practices effectively.

V. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This research offers a perspective on what influences educators in higher education when it comes to embracing and utilizing online teaching methods. By utilizing the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as a guide, the goal of the investigation was to pinpoint the factors that play a role in how technology is accepted. The information can help in shaping policies and approaches that improve the digital learning experience for teachers and students [2].

VI. THE TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM)

The TAM depicted in Figure 1 below, is an extensively used model to determine the acceptance of technology amongst individuals. Stemming from the theories of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Planned Behaviour (TPB), the TAM integrated the 'belief-attitude-intention-behaviour' relationship into its philosophies, theorizing that perception of effectiveness, outlooks and behavioural intentions positively or negatively influences one's actual usage of a technology [13]. Numerous scholars have confirmed the efficacy of the TAM in examining the adoption and use of technology ([23], [10], [2]).

Figure 1. A depiction of the Technology Acceptance Model [13]

Both extrinsic and intrinsic factors have direct triggers on PEOU and PU with direct impacts on attitude. Factors, however, are not fixed but differ in context. For instance, technological availabilities and infrastructures in place, history and location of institution, institution fiscal levels, didactic and pedagogic culture, and academics attitude towards change. Other factors include individual beliefs, satisfaction, technological capabilities including computer anxiety, internet connectivity, and proper technological support and training [19]. According to scholars in reference [8], in unison habit and age can strongly influence technological practices. They posit that academics who are not in the habit of utilizing digital technologies frequently may not acclimatize to online teaching with ease and confidence.

A. The TAM Constructs Examined in Context of the Study

- (1) *Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)*: it can be defined as academics ease of using online teaching platforms and the easiness of engaging online. In other words, their level of belief that teaching with digital technologies entails less effort [6].
- (2) *Perceived Usefulness (PU)*: The extent to which academics believe that online teaching can improve their teaching effectiveness [14].
- (3) *Attitude Toward Using (AT)*: The strength of academics' belief that online teaching feels practical to them. Their general emotional response to online teaching practices [14].
- (4) *Behavioural Intentions (BI)*: This construct comprises the attitude-behaviour-intention (A-BI) connection. In this context, according to the TAM academics may conceptualize their plan to engage online and incorporate technology in their general didactic practices currently and in the future [14].

VII. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The TAM was correlated into the investigation to delve into various factors that impact online teaching practices. Basing the investigation on the Model's constructs, their philosophies and sequential processes, the research aimed at offering a thorough investigation of the various factors influencing technology adoption in a higher education setting [2]. These constructs are crucial for grasping how technology is adopted and have been confirmed through research in various situations ([13], [23]).

VIII. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design and Approach

The study implemented the ideologies of positivism and employed the techniques of quantitative methodology. The overall investigation was based on deductive reasoning and its prescribed principles. Drawing on the philosophies of the TAM, logical assumptions were formulated in relation to the research problem. These assumptions were designed to form logical sets of statements in order to gather numerical sets of data [24]. This method enabled a thorough investigation into the connections among the elements in the TAM in relation to online teaching practices, thus generating reliable data for evaluation.

B. Data Collection

Survey method of data collection using structured questionnaires were distributed to a diverse sample of lecturers at a major higher education institution in the KwaZulu Natal province of South Africa. The survey instrument included demographic information and deductive statements designed to measure the constructs of the TAM that were quantifiable using a 5-point Likert scale. This method is effective for gathering large amounts of data efficiently and is commonly used in similar studies on technology adoption [4].

C. Analytical Tools and Techniques

The collected data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and SPSS software. The statistical methods included descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. The numerical data was quantified and presented in the form of figures and tables. The statistical outcomes were described and further implications and deductions were drawn from the results of the data. Comparisons of findings amongst the participant members were illustrated to show their stance taken such as agreement, disagreement, and neutral stance, as well as inconsistencies. In addition, outcomes were compared to findings and outcomes mentioned in the various literatures in Chapter two of the study. SEM was utilized to assess the relationships between the TAM constructs and to validate the measurement model. Applying Path analysis, the study expounded on the casual associations between the constructs and examined and verified the hypothesized relationships between the constructs. These analytical techniques are appropriate for testing complex models and has been widely used in research on technology acceptance [22].

D. Ethical Considerations

Ethical consent was secured before gathering data. Participants were briefed on the study's objectives and were assured about confidentiality and the voluntary aspect of their involvement. Upholding ethical practices in research is essential for maintaining the integrity of the study and safeguarding participants [12].

E. Conclusion

In this section, the overall study setup, data collection methods, analytical tools, and main concepts of the TAM were covered. The following section will share the important discoveries from the data analysis process.

IX. KEY FINDINGS

A. Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents

According to the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, there is a relatively equal distribution of genders among the respondents, with a minor majority being male (52% male and 48% female). Given that the average age of survey respondents was 43, it can be inferred that they are people with extensive experience and knowledge in the field of education. These lecturers are advanced in their careers, as shown by the fact that they have, on average, accumulated twelve years of teaching experience. The fact that they possess this level of experience is of the utmost importance since it could mold their perspectives and their openness to adopting new methods of instruction, especially those that make use of the online space. This demographic snapshot provides a required background for the purpose of conducting an analysis of the subsequent data on attitudes and activities toward online training.

B. Exploratory and Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) were performed to grasp how the variables are organized and to pinpoint the survey items that best capture the underlying concepts. The Cronbach's alpha values confirmed the reliability of the measurement model; all constructs surpassed the minimum cutoff of 0.6, ranging from 0.619 to 0.846, indicating high internal consistency.

- 1) *Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)*: Generally, users described online teaching platforms as easy to use. This positive experience played a significant role in shaping their decision to adopt the technology. The high reliability score (Cronbach's alpha of 0.846) associated with the PEOU framework highlights the relevance of user-friendliness in the context of technology adoption among academics.
- 2) *Perceived Usefulness (PU)*: The belief of educators in the ability of online teaching to improve their effectiveness played a significant role in motivating them to use digital technologies. The PU construct also showed high consistency (with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.836), highlighting the importance of perceived usefulness in adopting technology.
- 3) *Attitude Toward Using (AT)*: Educators showed a willingness to embrace online teaching methods. This outlook plays a key role in influencing how perceived usefulness and ease of use drive actual use and practices of online teaching. The AT construct demonstrated a reliability score of 0.775.
- 4) *Behavioral Intention (BI)*: Academics were very keen on keeping up with online teaching methods. Behavioral intention plays a significant role in how technology is used. The reliability score for the BI construct was 0.619, showing a moderate level of reliability.

C. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Results

The findings of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) confirmed the expected connections among the TAM components. The study showed a significant positive correlation between PEOU and AT ($p = 0.018$) as well as between AT and BI ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that ease of use and positive attitudes have a substantial impact on the intention to use online teaching platforms.

D. Discussion of Findings

The results align with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), showing that ease of use and perceived usefulness play crucial roles in influencing attitudes and intentions towards adopting technology. The strong reliability and validity of the model support the effectiveness of the TAM in understanding technology adoption among academics in higher education contexts. The research findings provide valuable insights into the factors that affect the use of online teaching aids. The study emphasizes two essential factors: the ease of use and the perceived value, both of which significantly influence educators' choices to include new technologies into their teaching methods. Online teaching platform were initially popular for their simplicity. In encouraging educators to use new technology, Cronbach's alpha value for the Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) construct emphasizes user-friendly interfaces. Lecturers feel more confident using systems with simple user-friendly interfaces. These systems' user-friendliness decreases early learning challenges and improves user experience, making instructors more willing to utilize them. The perceived utility (PU) of online teaching resources also affects educators' utilization of them. Online platforms are more likely to be used by lecturers if they believe they can improve education and student performance. A high reliability score for the PU construct shows that educators recognize the importance of contemporary technology in making instruction more efficient and engaging. Academics desire to learn and use new technology depends on their perception of its usefulness.

The research also shows that a positive attitude toward online teaching techniques (Attitude Toward Using, or AT) is essential for effective utilization. Positive individuals are more likely to embrace and investigate online instructional technology, increasing adoption rates. The correlation between reported ease of use, perceived usefulness and positive attitudes, indicates how these factors affect academics' behavior. The construct of Behavioral Intention (BI) further reinforces the notion that educators are eager to persist in utilizing online instructional approaches in the future. Despite the somewhat lower dependability score for BI compared to the other constructs, it still indicates a moderate to high level of commitment among educators to retain and perhaps increase their

utilization of online teaching resources. The level of intention is a crucial indicator of how likely academics are to really use these technologies. The previously stated implies that as they grow more knowledgeable and at ease with these technologies, they are more likely to start using them.

The results of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) offer strong evidence that supports the validity of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in the higher education setting. The strong positive correlations shown between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Attitude (AT), as well as between AT and Behavioral Intention (BI), confirm the model's effectiveness in explaining technology adoption behaviors among higher education academics. These findings highlight the importance of educational institutions prioritizing the improvement of both the user-friendliness and perceived efficacy of online teaching platforms in order to encourage their wider use.

To summarize, this research provides significant insights for decision-makers and educational administrators who aim to enhance the implementation of digital teaching techniques in higher education. Institutions may foster an atmosphere that promotes the use and integration of online teaching resources by focusing on the creation of adaptable and highly efficient solutions. In addition, providing continuous support and training for educators may further bolster their confidence and proficiency in utilizing these technologies, resulting in more efficient and captivating teaching approaches.

X. INTERPRETING THE FINDINGS

The results of this research confirm that the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is useful in explaining how higher education faculty members adopt online teaching platforms. Factors such as Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) have a notable impact on academics' views towards incorporating online teaching approaches. These findings align with prior research, underscoring the significance of user-friendly and efficient digital resources in shaping positive attitudes towards technology integration ([13], [23]). The research discovered that Perceived Ease of Use strongly influences educators' attitudes toward online instruction. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.846 signified reliability within this framework, implying that lecturers' tendency to embrace online platforms is heightened when they perceive them as less complex and manageable. This highlights the significance of creating digital teaching resources that are both intuitive and accessible. Perceived Usefulness held significant importance in adopting technology, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.836. Lecturers are more likely to embrace online teaching platforms when they view these tools as enhancing their effectiveness, aligning with the premise of the TAM that perceived benefits influence technology acceptance [23].

The study showed that lecturers had a positive attitude towards online teaching, with a reliability score of 0.775 for the AT construct. This plays a crucial role in linking PEOU, PU, and system usage. It emphasizes the importance of cultivating positive attitudes by creating platforms that are easy to use and beneficial in boosting adoption levels. With a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.619, the willingness to utilize online teaching practices emerged as a moderately consistent factor. The fact that there is such a strong desire in continuing to use these strategies is a reflection of how much educators appreciate the benefits they provide. User experience and attitudes have a substantial impact on the desire to participate in the online environment, as shown by the markedly favorable links that exist between PEOU, AT, and BI.

XI. IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

The study highlights the significant role that policymakers and educational leaders at both institutional levels and national level play in enhancing the utilization of e-learning methods and digital systems. This can be accomplished by concentrating on digital tools that are user-friendly and less complex, highlighting the potential of these tools to improve teaching outcomes and results, offering and providing training programs to enhance perceptions of ease of use and usefulness, and cultivating an environment that provides a positive environment for the integration of technology. These will encourage and establish positive attitudes towards technology integration.

A. *Limitations of the Study*

The research provides important information, but it does have its limitations. For example, the group of participants, while diverse, might not be completely representative of all higher education faculty members. Moreover, relying on self-assessments for the study could introduce biases.

B. *Directions for Future Research*

Future studies should consider increasing both the sample size and diversity to improve the generalizability of the findings. Longitudinal research could help gain a better understanding of how attitudes and intentions towards online teaching methods change over time. It would also be beneficial to explore how training programs influence the adoption of technology.

XII. CONCLUSION AND FINAL THOUGHTS

From this research it is evident that Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) play essential roles in academics embracing online teaching methods and practices. Positive attitudes towards digitization of teaching serve as a mediator in influencing Behavioral Intention (BI) based on the relationship between these factors. These results validate the effectiveness of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in clarifying how educational professionals adopt technology in their practice. The study adds to the existing knowledge by offering real-life examples of how academic staff in higher education are influenced to adopt technology. It highlights the significance of easy-to-use digital tools in shaping attitudes and willingness to embrace technology. The study suggests the following recommendations for policymakers and educational leaders:

Support the creation and use of educational technology platforms.

Create greater awareness by highlighting the advantages and benefits of online teaching practices in enhancing teaching effectiveness.

Offer continuous training and assistance to help higher education academics become skilled in utilizing digital resources.

Promote a welcoming environment that emphasizes and motivates the integration of technology in education.

Constructive implementation of online teaching amongst higher education academics is a critical factor for institutions that are ambitious about steering digital teaching and learning practices. Undoubtedly, though, globally there is a reluctant tendency amongst academics to engage with the online environment and some even show resistance. Given the current state of affairs, it is of utmost importance to investigate the elements that impact the adoption of online teaching by academics of higher education. The purpose of this study was to conduct investigation using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in order to provide significant insights into how to increase the acceptance and utilization of web-based teaching and instructional resources. For continued

development and escalating involvement in the online space and to successfully alter higher education, it is essential to encourage a constructive mentality and to demonstrate the advantages of the many digital teaching methods and digital platforms that are now available.

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